

First-Year Results from a Space-based Sporadic-E Detector

Bruce A. Fritz, Kenneth F. Dymond, Ellen J. Wagner, Andrew C. Nicholas, Scott A. Budzien, and Andrew W. Stephan

U.S. Naval Research Laboratory
4555 Overlook Ave SW
Washington, DC 20375
USA

Corresponding Author: bruce.fritz@nrl.navy.mil

ABSTRACT

The Triple Magnesium Ionospheric Photometer (Tri-MIP) has been developed as a 1U CubeSat compatible sensor to detect a mid-ultraviolet (MUV), Mg^+ doublet emission near 280 nm as a tracer of Sporadic-E (E_s). The initial flight of Tri-MIP is on the Slingshot-1 spacecraft that launched into a circular orbit at an altitude of 500 km and an inclination of 45°. Paired with a 1U scanning ultraviolet mirror (SUV) on the Slingshot-1 spacecraft, Tri-MIP provides altitude profiles of Mg^+ airglow emissions through limb scans of Earth's ionosphere along the wake direction of the orbit. Tri-MIP is especially well-suited for E_s detection and may allow for the observation of faint signatures of E_s that are otherwise not visible with other commonly used, remote plasma detection methods, such as ground-based ionosondes or GPS radio occultation experiments. These proceedings will focus on a summary of results from the first year of operations on orbit for the Slingshot-1 Tri-MIP.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sporadic-E (E_s) is a phenomenon where thin layers of charged particles coalesce to create a highly localized, anomalous layer of ionization in Earth's E-region ionosphere, typically at an altitude between 90 km and 160 km. Regions of E_s are characterized by a high concentration of metal ions, primarily Mg^+ and Fe^+ , that are deposited by meteor ablation in the atmosphere. The metal ions converge in thin layers, often due to wind shears at low and mid-latitudes. Height distribution, layer thickness, and density of E_s of layers significantly impact HF signal propagation by creating an unexpected source of refraction for radio frequencies up to the VHF region of the spectrum.

The U.S. Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has developed a new experiment for E_s detection through remote sensing of ionospheric Mg^+ from a space-based, CubeSat-compatible sensor. The Experiment for Characterizing the Lower Ionosphere & Prediction of Sporadic-E (ECLIPSE) is a compact, highly-sensitive instrument built by the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory for observing the Earth's bottom-side ionosphere to characterize plasma density structures and for observing the spatial distribution of Mg^+ ions generated by meteor ablation [Dymond *et al.*, 2023]. The ECLIPSE suite of instruments is based on a legacy of photometric airglow sensors developed at NRL, such as the Triple-Tiny Ionospheric Photometer (Tri-TIP) [Nicholas *et al.*, 2019] and the Triple Magnesium Ion Photometer (Tri-MIP) [Nicholas *et al.*, 2021]. The Tri-MIP instrument was first flown on the Slingshot-1 Mission, which this paper will briefly summarize.

2. INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION

The Tri-MIP is a 1U (10 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm) photometric sensor to measure the Mg II ²S-²P doublet at 279.55 – 280.27 nm as a means to derive Mg⁺ density in the ionosphere. A set of three, matched photometers are used to measure (1) the primary Mg II 280 nm emission, (2) a nearby Molecular Nitrogen Vegard-Kaplan (0,6) emission at 277 nm, and (3) the background radiation environment. Each Tri-MIP (and Tri-TIP) is paired with a 1U Scanning Ultraviolet Mirror (SUVM) assembly to vary the look direction and image either the limb or disk.

The Slingshot-1 mission is a 12U CubeSat mission that launched on 1 July 2022 with a single Tri-MIP / SUVM pair flown as a Risk Reduction for the full ECLIPSE mission (ECLIPSE-RR). The instrument is oriented in the spacecraft wake direction to scan the Earth’s limb in the orbital plane. ECLIPSE-RR completed its on-orbit testing phase in November 2022 and has been operating routinely from late November through the writing of these proceedings in June 2023.

3. RESULTS

Data have been processed to a minimum of L1A level (geolocated and time-tagged) for 6 months of Slingshot data from December 2022 through May 2023. Figure 1 shows an example limb scan made by ECLIPSE-RR on 21 December, 2022 between 10:36:23 UT and 11:29:43 UT. The map on the left illustrates the ground track of the spacecraft trajectory during the observation, illustrated by the white line with red dots that represent grid points for subsequent Level 2 processing (tomographic images). Figure 1 also shows the basic output from the instrument, on the right, in terms of counts in each channel of the instrument.

Figure 1: ECLIPSE-RR observation made on 21 December, 2022 between 10:36:23 UT and 11:29:43 UT. The map on the left illustrates the spacecraft trajectory ground track during the observation with a white line; the red dots are the grid points used in Level 2 processing. The yellow dot represents the sub-solar point at the mid-point of the dayside pass (~11.05 UT) and the blue parallel lines represent the geomagnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ geomagnetic latitude. The plot on the right represents the raw count output from the instrument for each of the 3 photometer channels (Mg II, N₂ V-K, and dark background) as a function of time and position.

The red line represents the primary channel (Mg⁺), the blue line shows the neighboring N₂ emission (VK), and the black line is the system noise background. The oscillating nature of the

Mg^+ and VK signals represents the natural variation in signal strength as the FOV moves up and down. The airglow being measured naturally gets brighter as the instrument measures lower in the atmosphere. The “dark” channel shows a generally quiet system background except in this example the shows a pass through the South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA). The background subtracted data are then used to generate a tomographic image from both channels, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sample tomographic output from the ECLIPSE-RR observations made on 21 December, 2022 for three consecutive orbits between 10:36:23 UT – 11:29:43 UT (top row), 12:10:39 UT – 13:03:59 UT (middle row), and 13:44:56 UT – 14:38:16 UT (bottom row). The figures on the left show altitude profiles of Mg^+ (cm^{-3}) as a function of Orbit Phase Angle. The figures on the right show altitude profiles of Volume Emission Rate (VER, photons/ cm^3/s) for the N_2 V-K emission. The light blue lines in both figures illustrate magnetic latitude.

The tomographic images shown in Figure 2 are generated using the Least Squares Positive Definite (LSPD) algorithm, described in detail elsewhere [Dymond *et al.*, 2017], so specifics are deferred in this report. In general, the plots on the left shows layered structure in the Mg^+ density at ~ 120 km. The high-altitude Mg^+ enhancement seen near 90° orbit phase angle geographic latitude is frequently seen and will be discussed further in the next section. The plot on the right shows the direct inversion product derived from the N_2 V-K emission channel. This provides a check on the inversion process by verifying the general structure of the background atmosphere. For further comparison, an orbital pass that does not cross the equator is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Example ECLIPSE-RR dayside pass from 5 December 2022 from 22:02:04 UT – 22:55:24 UT. The map on the left illustrates the orbit ground track from the observing pass with the subsolar point indicated by the yellow dot. The plot on the right shows the Mg^+ density retrieved through the tomographic retrieval process.

The example shown in Figure 3 is from 5 December 2022 between 22:02:04 UT and 22:55:24 UT. The map on the left shows the dayside pass on this day is in the southern hemisphere over the Pacific Ocean. The plot on the right shows noticeable layered structure in the Mg^+ data at ~ 120 km. In this case, however, the orbital pass does not cross the equator and the large, vertical density structure observed near the equator in Figure 2 is not present.

ECLIPSE-RR operated in a secondary “disk stare” mode in addition to the limb scans. The scan mirror has a wide enough range of motion to look 45° below the horizon, which points the FOV at the Earth’s surface. The instrument was operated in this “disk stare” mode for approximately 2 months as part of the Risk Reduction for the full ECLIPSE mission. Figure 3 shows an example of the data collected for 3 consecutive orbits on 27 February, 2023.

Figure 4: A sample of disk scan data from February 27, 2023 between 3:12:59 UT and 7:17:09 UT. The map on the left shows the Slingshot-1 orbits with the observed Mg^+ radiance color encoded. The light blue lines indicate the magnetic equator and $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic latitudes. The sub-solar point is indicated by the yellow ovoid, which starts at $\sim 135^\circ$ E longitude and continues westward to $\sim 70^\circ$ E. The data gather starts near Southern Africa indicated by the blue asterisk. Nighttime measurements are shown in black, as no counts were observed (as expected) by the Tri-MIP. The plot on the right shows Mg^+ radiances as a function of UT.

The bright signals in the Mg^+ radiance plot shown in Figure 4 shows significant small-scale structuring over the course of three consecutive dayside passes over the Asian continent. The instrument remained powered on through the nightside portion of the orbit but there is no signal without solar excitation as a driver.

4. DISCUSSION & SUMMARY

The ability to observe E_s globally on a routine basis will provide new insight into the occurrence rates and global morphology. Bottom-side variation is not well understood on a global basis, and the vertical structure that appears in the Mg^+ tomographic images is particularly interesting. The vertical Mg^+ emission feature, in particular, has previously been observed in a similar manner. The Visual Airglow Experiment on Atmospheric Explorer E (AE-E) observed the 280 nm doublet from a polar orbit [Fesen and Hays, 1982] and measured the high-altitude Mg^+ profile on nearly 2/3 of orbits, generally near the equator in the afternoon. This generally agrees with the observed behavior observed by ECLIPSE-RR, however the coverage is not yet regular enough to say with certainty. The follow-on full ECLIPSE mission will have routine operations to fill in the observational gaps. Subsequent modeling efforts were able to show qualitatively reasonable agreement between the AE-E measurements and a physics-based modeling approach [Fesen *et al.*, 1983]. The previous work solved coupled continuity and momentum equations for one major (O^+) and one minor (Mg^+) species to show the agreement, but acknowledge a number of discrepancies arise in the details and inadequacies in the model used left several unanswered questions, that perhaps may be answerable with Tri-MIP data, both by ECLIPSE-RR and ECLIPSE.

Approximately 6 months of ECLIPSE-RR data have been processed to a minimum L1A level, starting after the completion of early orbit testing in mid-November 2022. First, limb scan observations ran from mid-November 2022 through 25 February 2022. L2 data is processed for Dec. 2022 and is still a work in progress. Starting on 26 February, ECLIPSE-RR began collecting data in the disk stare mode for 2 months. Limb operations were resumed on 27 April 2023 and have been running as mission resources allow. Figure 4 shows a summary of the data that have been collected and process through 28 May 2023, broken down by data type. Slingshot-1/ECLIPSE-RR L1A data will be

made available immediately on a request basis. The data will be hosted on a publicly accessible database that has not yet been determined.

The primary mission for ECLIPSE is the Space Test Program Houston 9 (STP-H9), which launched in March 2023 to the International Space Station. ECLIPSE was turned on within days of launch and has been successfully operating since powered on in late March. The expected end of mission for ECLIPSE-RR on Slingshot-1 is 1 July 2023, which provides time for mission overlap and coincident measurements.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Tri-MIP development was originally funded under the DARPA SEE program, analysis has been funded by the Office of Naval Research through NRL 6.1 base funding. ECLIPSE-RR was integrated and flown by the DoD STP

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